

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي السادس للتنمية المستدامة والمجال

Book of Proceedings 6th International Congress on Sustainable Development and Space

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6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

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6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

مقدمة

يواجه العالم تحديات كبيرة في إقامة توازن بين التنمية المستدامة والحفاظ على البيئة من جهة ومن جهة أخرى تحقيق الأمن الغذائي والذي أصبح من أولويات الدول بفعل الاحتكار واختلال التوازن بين الطلب والإنتاج، ففي الوقت الذي يواصل فيه الاعتماد على الطرق التقليدية في الزراعة المعتمدة أساساً على تساقط الأمطار والاستهلاك المفرط للمياه الجوفية غير المتجددة، فإن هذا له أثراً كبيراً على نزوب الموارد الاقتصادية غير المتجددة واستقرار الأمن الغذائي بالعالم. ولذلك يتجه العالم إلى مصادر الطاقة المتجددة والبحث عن بدائل تضمن احتياجات السكان وفق مبدأ التنمية المستدامة.

وتعد الطاقة المتجددة بأنها الحل الأخير لمشاكل الطاقة والبيئة في العالم، مما يتيح إمكانية الطاقة الرخيصة وغير المحدودة تقريباً الخالية من التلوث، حيث نجد بأن العالم يستهلك الطاقة من مصادر عديدة، فمنها المصادر التي تأتي من خامات الوقود الأحفوري مثل الفحم والنفط والغاز الطبيعي، ومنها الطاقة التي تأتي من مصادر صناعية مثل الطاقة النووية. كما يحصل على الطاقة أيضاً من مصادر طبيعية مثل الطاقة الشمسية والطاقة المستخلصة من الرياح ومساقط المياه والتي تسمى بمصادر الطاقة المتجددة.

إن المشاكل المتفاقمة من خلال أزمات الطاقة والتخوف من اختلال الأمن الغذائي ولاسيما في الدول الأكثر فقراً، يستوجب إعادة التفكير بشكل جوهري على المستوى الدولي وفق استراتيجيات مستدامة تحقق الاستقرار على مستوى العالم وتجنباً الوقوع في أزمات دولية تتركز أساساً على الاستغلال العقلاني للموارد الطبيعية واعتماد طاقات متجددة وأساليب جديدة في الزراعة لضمان تحقيق استدامة في الأمن الغذائي والحفاظ على حقوق الأجيال القادمة.

د. صيد وحمد سفيان

رئيس اللجنة العلمية

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Preface

The world faces great challenges in balancing sustainable development and environmental preservation with achieving food security, which has become a priority for countries due to the monopoly and imbalance between demand and production, while continuing to rely on traditional agricultural methods based mainly on rainfall and excessive consumption of non-renewable groundwater, This has a significant impact on the depletion of non-renewable economic resources and the stability of global food security. Therefore, the world is turning to renewable energy sources and is looking for alternatives that guarantee the needs of the population in accordance with the principle of sustainable development.

Renewable energy promises to be the latest solution to the world's energy and environmental problems, allowing for the possibility of cheap and nearly unlimited energy, free of pollution, as we find that the world consumes energy from many sources, including sources from fossil fuel ores such as coal, oil and natural gas, and energy from industrial sources such as nuclear power. It also draws energy from natural sources such as solar, wind and watersheds called renewable energy sources.

The problems exacerbated by the energy crises and the fear of the occupation of food security, especially in the poorest countries, require a fundamental rethinking at the international level in accordance with sustainable strategies that ensure stability at the global level and avoid falling into international crises based mainly on the rational exploitation of natural resources and the adoption of renewable energies and new methods of agriculture to ensure the sustainability of food security and preservation of the rights of future generations.

Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Soufiane

President of the Scientific Committee

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

ÖN SÖZ

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 5 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye'den 16, Türkiye dışından da 8 ülkeden (Cezayir, Çin, Fas, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri) 53 bildiri yer almaktadır. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltmelerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildirilere ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Bu kitapta kongrede sunum yapan bilim insanlarının bildirinin tam metinleri yer almaktadır. Kongreye iştirak edemeyen ve bu konulara ilgi duyan kimselerin metinlerden istifade edebilmesini sağlayacak olan bu çalışmanın bilim dünyasına hayırlara vesile olmasını diliyorum.

15.10.2024

Prof. Dr. Şinasi Akdemir

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

İçindekiler - فهرس - Contents

Experimental Study Of Cascade Solar Still 1

H. Menous

S. Allal

A. Bendahou

O. Cheknane

A. Hamid

La résilience territoriale face aux enjeux du développement durable, cas du village lauréat du concours du village le plus propre dans la wilaya de Tizi-Ouzou, Algérie. 10

Karima Idres

Lotfi Mokrani

Kamel Moulai

The Relationship Between Melting and Dripping Behavior of PP Thermoplastic Polymers Due to The Furnace Test 22

Mastura A. Abdoalshafie Efhema

33.....التنمية المستدامة ومجاليات التدوير الفني في تونس: تجربة الفنان الطيب بالحاج أحمد نموذجاً
د. هندا بوحامد

53.....واقع الطاقات المتجددة في تحقيق التنمية المستدامة بالمملكة العربية السعودية"
د. إلهام شيلي

70.....الوكالة الجزائرية لترقية الاستثمار ضمن القانون 18-22
الدكتور لعابسة طارق

85.....التنمية البيئية المستدامة من منظور شرعي
د. جيداء رجب صيام

Dergipark'ta "Türkiye'nin Çevre Sorunlarına Yönelik Tutumlar" Başlığı Altında Yapılan Çalışmaların İncelenmesi* 98

Furkan Doğru

Prof. Dr. Asım Çoban

The Relationship Between Melting and Dripping Behavior of PP Thermoplastic Polymers Due To The Furnace Test 114

Mastura A. Abdoalshafie Efhema

Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Çevre Bilincini Ele Alan Çalışmaların İncelenmesi* . 126

Furkan Doğru

Prof. Dr. Asım Çoban

Experimental Study Of Cascade Solar Still

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Abstract

Solar distillation is the most cost-effective and economically competitive desalination technique to overcome the need for freshwater in few production, especially in arid areas where solar energy is abundant.

The objective of this work is to realize and experiment a cascade solar distiller also to study the influence of certain parameters namely: salinity rate, wind speed, cooling of the glass , and the increase of solar radiation by concentration.

The results obtained do not really illustrate the influence of the salinity, on the other side the production has increased for the cooling of the glass. The concentration of solar radiation caused a rise in the external temperature of the glass which led to a fall in production.

Keywords : Cascade solar still, Brine, cooling the glass, reflector.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Introduction

Water is the essential element of all life on earth since the creation of the universe, but it tends to become a rare commodity because its total quantity on earth has remained stable for more than 3.5 billion years. It has appeared, and consumption continues to decline as a result of population growth and rising living standards, the average consumption is of the order of 137 liters per day and 600 m³ / inhabitant / year [1]. In Algeria, the problem of potable water supply has already been raised.

Firstly, mechanisms must be put in place to reduce wastage and water leakage, because this substance remains insufficient. One of the solutions is the production of fresh water from salt water. However, desalination requires energy whose cost is important. For this purpose, projects in the field of solar energy have shown since 1872 that solar distillation is economically more competitive when the demand for fresh water is not too great. By its privileged location, Algeria has the largest solar deposit in the Mediterranean basin. The average duration of sunshine of the Algerian territory exceeds the 2000 annual hours, to reach almost 3500 hours of sunshine in the Sahara Desert.[2].

. To address this, various enhancements are being studied. For instance, Research on solar stills reveals various strategies for enhancing their efficiency, especially in areas with limited freshwater access. Velmurugan et al. [3] showed that adding fins increases daily production up to 2.8 kg/m², while Al-Ghamdi et al. [4] demonstrated that phase-change materials (PCM) can store heat, sustaining nighttime productivity. Inclined solar stills, designed by Aybar et al. [6] and Sadineni et al. [7], improve evaporation and condensation with better solar exposure and reduced air space. Tabrizi et al. [5] examined cascade-type stills, showing that high water flow reduces productivity by lowering internal heat and mass transfer rates. Dunkle et al. [8] and Hongfei et al. [9] refined thermal transfer models for solar stills, indicating that productivity depends on optimized transfer coefficients, design, and environmental factors.

Additionally, Tripathi et al.[10] and Nafey et al.[11] highlighted that water depth significantly impacts solar still productivity, with shallower depths accelerating evaporation and increasing output. Multi-stage solar stills, which minimize water depth, are particularly effective for enhancing performance.

I.PRESENTATION OF THE PROTOTYPE

I. 1. Presentation of the Prototype

The experimental system consists essentially of a cascading solar still. The lid is made of glass. The inclination of the cover is about 36 ° relative to the horizontal to have the maximum of sunshine. A layer of polystyrene Fig. 1 provides insulation.

The tests carried out, in Blida, in a place where the distiller was exposed to the solar rays so that it can capture the maximum of solar radiation without any obstruction, which presents the following characteristics: : 36°28'12"North. Longitude: 2°49'39"East, The various tests carried out during the summer period, allowed us to measure the daily production of distilled water for a period ranging from (9h30mn) in the morning until (15h30mn) in the evening. A thermometer was used to measure the ambient temperature.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Fig.1. Diagram of the cascade solar still

II.2. Different techniques during experimental study

Fig. 2 shows the importance of the temperature of the glass pane by two methods: cooling of the outer pane by a fan (forced convection) and cooling of the outer pane by water runoff. We also study the concentration of solar radiation inside the system using aluminum reflector as shown in the Fig. 3

Fig.2. Cooling the outside of surface

Fig.3. Use of reflectors.

III.1 using different brakish water concentrations

II.RESULTS AND DISCUION

In our experiments we used different brine concentrations (tap water, 10% of sea water, 50% of sea water ,90% of sea water , 100% of sea water, sea water +40g of salt),to see its influence on production in six days different.

Take into account that each day it has these characteristics concerning the solar

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

illumination, the ambient temperature and the speed of the wind.

The results show in the figure that the production was reached its maximum 1650 ml when the tap water was used compared to the other brine Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Cumulative production for different salinity.

III.2. Using ventilation

To cool the outside of the glass by forced convection, we used a fan installed at a distance of one meter in front of the glass. The fan speed is fixed at 6m / s.

According to the table we note that the difference between the temperature of the glazing and the brine varies between 5 and 10 C and that the cumulative production has reached 1720 ml (the highest quantity obtained has been explained by the fact that the fan increases the convection exchange that causes a cooling of the glass, so the increase in production).

Table 1. Expérimental values obtained by ventilation

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

T(h)	Vitre ext	Temp int	Temp ambiante
09.30	43.7	55.9	25
10.30	48.3	64.4	25
11.30	44.7	61.4	26
12.30	48.3	62.1	28
13.30	45.3	59	28
14.30	45.8	57.7	27
15.30	42.9	52.9	25

T(h)	Temperature (C°)		
	Bac	Saumure	Vitre int
09.30	49.3	58.7	48.8
10.30	63.3	68.4	53.3
11.30	64.2	66.4	51.4
12.30	67	66.7	55.6
13.30	66.3	62.5	51.1
14.30	65.9	60.0	51.1
15.30	59.4	56	47

T(h)	Production (ml)	
	Eclairment (w/m ²)	Production (ml)
09.30	664.15	0
10.30	761.32	140
11.30	851.88	410
12.30	844.90	810
13.30	91.50	1160
14.30	714.15	1450
15.30	452.83	1720

III.3 cooling the exterior of the glass

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

The third technique that we used for cooling the exterior face of the glass is the water runoff, the principle consists in running a quantity of cold water on the exterior face of the glass, and the results obtained are shown in the table.

According to the results obtained in Table 2, it can be noted that this technique has also made it possible to slightly increase production.

Table 2. Experimental values obtained by water runoff

T(h)	Température (C°)		
	Bac	Saumur	Vitre int
09.30	45.2	54.2	46.1
10.30	62.1	64	60.3
11.30	64.9	66.3	61.4
12.30	72.2	71.0	62.8
13.30	72.6	67.6	65.7
14.30	67.3	63.58	58.2
15.30	68.7	54.8	48.6

T(h)	Température (C°)		
	Vitre ext	Temp int	Temp ambiante
09.30	40.9	50.2	25
10.30	53	66	25
11.30	55.25	69.7	27
12.30	60	70.6	28
13.30	58.6	66.9	28
14.30	56.3	58.2	29
15.30	44.5	48.6	28

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

T(h)	Production (ml)	
	Eclairment (w/m ²)	Production (ml)
09.30	625.47	0
10.30	750.94	120
11.30	805.66	330
12.30	815.09	690
13.30	787.73	1090
14.30	521.69	1490
15.30	593.39	1720

III.4. Using reflectors

The experiment consists of placing aluminum-covered plates next to the distiller. The purpose of this experiment is to concentrate the solar radiation inside the still. According to the table 3 we see that both sides of the glass (outer and inner) have reached very high values, this caused a decrease in the amount of condensed water because the condensation increases when the temperature of the glass is cold.

Table 3. Experimental values obtained by the use of reflectors

Temp (h)	Temperature (ml)		
	Bac	Saumure	Vitre int
09.30	40	41	36
10.30	49.8	50	40
11.30	68.1	54.3	62
12.30	75.3	60.3	70.25
13.30	76.7	59.7	70.38
14.30	75.4	56.3	63.2
15.00	75.5	57	59.57
15.30	70.4	53.3	55.36

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Temperature (ml)			
Temp (h)	Vitre ext	Temp int	Temp ambiante
09.30	35.25	55.2	25
10.30	50.2	67.1	25
11.30	71.7	75.1	26
12.30	79.2	80.2	28
13.30	77.3	79.8	28
14.30	69.5	76.5	27
15.00	65.3	74.4	26
15.30	63.2	63.9	26

Production (ml)		
Temp (h)	Éclaircement (w/m ²)	Production (ml)
09.30	336.79	0
10.30	363.79	30
11.30	832.07	100
12.30	889.62	340
13.30	889.62	600
14.30	801.88	980
15.00	751.88	1070
15.30	611.32	1200

The figure below shows the influence of cooling of exterior glazing on the production of distilled water compared to other methods where production could reach 1720 ml Fig. 5

Fig.5. Production by different methodes

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Conclusion

- The production, the temperature of each component depends on the solar illuminance, the ambient temperature and the wind speed.
- The six-day measurement companion on several brines with different salinity levels showed that their influence on thermal performance and production is minimal.
- The cooling of the external face of the glass by forced convection (use of a fan with a speed of 6m / s), and by trickling (cooling every half hour) has allowed an increase in production.
- On the other hand, the use of reflectors to focus solar irradiance on the inside of the still caused the temperature on the outside of the glass to rise (around 80 ° C), resulting in a drop in production.

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